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“MARY JOY”

She had been waiting for this day since last week.

Three o'clock. Beach. Friends. Laughter.

She had replayed it in her mind so many times that it already felt real.

That morning, she woke up early. The sky was still soft and pale when she jogged around the neighborhood. She jogged on different schedules depending on the time she woke up. Today was a bit different. She felt excited.

On her way home, she bought hot pandesal. Coffee and pandesal were part of her morning routine.

While walking, she saw a familiar woman wearing a long skirt. It was her neighbor, the one who owned the sari-sari store across her apartment. The store was already open.

“Why does she wake up so early?” she said to herself.

“Good morning, Joy. Done jogging today?” Auntie Linda called out.

She smiled and nodded.

Auntie Linda was the first person who approached her when she was looking for an apartment. She was too friendly—maybe nosy, or maybe both. Joy was not sure if Auntie Linda had a child or a husband. She seemed alone, always busy with her store. But she closed the store early, and no one in the neighborhood knew what Auntie Linda did when no one was around.

An old man passing by laughed lightly. “Sexy na si Joy oh. Exercise every day.”

She did not answer. She only smiled again, smaller this time, and hurried upstairs.

“She’s still not friendly to the neighborhood,” Auntie Linda told the man.

Inside her apartment, silence welcomed her.

She checked her phone. Messages. Notifications. She shared a post about kindness and peace of mind. It felt right to do so.

She made coffee and took photos before taking her first sip. Then she remembered the pandesal she had bought. She ate it and thought about how plain her life was. She felt blank and stared at the ceiling for a few minutes. Then she looked at the window and saw the curtains hanging still. Not even a light wind passed by at that moment.

Plain. Boring. All the time.

She finished her coffee and took a bath. She imagined herself wearing a beautiful dress that day. She wanted to look beautiful when she went outside.

She held the white dress against her body. In the mirror, she looked hopeful. Confident. Almost glowing.

Before leaving, she opened the fridge to check for lunch. An old plastic ice cream container caught her eye. She opened it.

Menudo.

The one her mother had given her weeks ago.

She stared at it for a moment. Then she slowly drained it into the sink. The sauce slid down like something tired and forgotten.

“It’s been a long time now,” she whispered. “I miss my parents. I miss my siblings.”

She always planned to go home, but for some reason she couldn’t.

At 10:55 AM, she rode a tricycle to the church. She worried she would be late, but the Mass had not started yet. The priest was a little late too.

She sat near the door and looked around. Familiar faces were scattered like memories.

An old friend was there, carrying a baby. Joy smiled at her, but her friend was busy soothing the child. In front of her sat a complete family. The mother wore an elegant blue dress. The father had a blue polo shirt tucked neatly into his belt, polished brown leather shoes shining under the light. Their daughter wore baggy jeans and sneakers with an almost cropped blouse. The young brother watched random YouTube videos, his tiny blue shoes tapping against the bench.

She smiled. Then she looked away. There were almost no vacant seats.

She noticed a child eating biscuits. Another one was sleeping. A man she recognized sat a few rows away—the one who once went viral because of a scandal involving a third party.

“He looked weird in those glasses,” she whispered.

The woman beside her smiled, thinking Joy was talking to her.

Then the priest’s voice filled the church.

“Mao nang maghinulsol kita sa atong mga sala...”

The words came like lightning—bright and fast—but they did not fully reach her. Her eyes wandered again.

Two couples wearing pastel colors sat nearby. They looked perfect together. The man carried the woman’s bag.

If only she were shorter... or if he were a little taller than her, she thought.

She sang the Lord’s Prayer. Closed her eyes. Clasped her hands.

“Hinunoa, luwasa kami... luwasa kami sa dautan...”

When it was time for Holy Communion, she hesitated. The line was long but orderly.

Then she saw her.

A woman with bob-cut hair. The same woman who once asked her an insensitive question that stayed with her for days.

The woman was coming closer.

Before their eyes could meet, Joy stood up and quietly inserted herself into the line. She did not want to smile.

In her mind, in her heart, she knew she hated that woman.

“Amen,” she said when the host was placed on her tongue.

She knelt down and prayed hard.

After Mass, she went straight to the station. A seat was reserved for her.

“Attended Mass again?” Kuya Ronie asked with a grin. “You’re really kind and religious, Joy.”

She smiled. “Thank you, Kuya.”

She even paid extra.

When she reached her apartment building, Auntie Linda called out.

“Joy! A parcel came for you! Where were you?”

“I went to Mass.”

“Wow. Such a good and religious girl. That’s why you’re blessed.”

She smiled and thanked her. She carried the parcel upstairs.

At 2:45 PM, messages from her friends started coming in. She changed clothes, getting ready for the beach. Then a photo popped up.

It was him.

The guy she liked.

Beside him was the woman he was courting. They looked close. Comfortable.

Joy stared at the photo for a long time.

Then she reacted with a laughing emoji.

She placed the phone down. Took a deep breath. Composed herself.

Before leaving, she decided to open the parcel. She smiled while opening the box, careful and slow. When she saw what was inside, her smile softened.

She placed it on her bedside.

The afternoon passed. The beach, the noise, the pretending. She laughed when needed. She smiled in pictures.

When she came home that night, the room was quiet again.

She went straight to her bedside.

There it was.

A slender silicone apostrophe.

She held it gently in her hands.

A small curve.

A quiet mark.

Early the next morning, she heard Auntie Linda scream outside.

Joy did not want to get out of bed. She was still sleepy. Instead of checking the window, she hid under the blanket.

“Mary Joy! Mary Joy! Your parcel is here! I accidentally switched our parcels yesterday!”

Joy jumped out of bed and ran toward the door. Her heart pounded. She felt nervous and almost froze when she saw Auntie Linda outside.

“I’m sorry, Joy,” Auntie Linda said. “I might have switched our parcels yesterday. I was about to open this last night, but good thing I saw your name.”

She pointed at the label.

Mary Joy slowly opened her hands as she received the parcel. Her hands were shaking.

Joy walked upstairs slowly, her mind racing.

The door closed behind her with a quiet click.

The box was still on the floor, open.

Beside the bed lay the small curved piece of silicone.

For a moment, she just stood there.

Auntie Linda’s voice rose from downstairs.

“Joy? Can I have my parcel?”

Joy looked at the object in her hand. The curve rested softly against her palm, light as punctuation.

Outside, the neighborhood was already awake. Tricycles passed. Someone laughed.

“Joy?” Auntie Linda called again.

Joy swallowed.

The morning suddenly felt too bright.